

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP3 - Development of the Virtual Ecosystem for
Research Activation (VERA)

D3.5. Collaboration tools and services
integration

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Deliverable 3.5

Collaboration tools and services integration

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Contents

I. Executive summary	4
I. Structure of the document	4
II. VERA Collaboration tools	5
III. Conclusions	10

I. Executive summary

This document accompanies the release of the “D3.5 - Collaboration tools and services integration”, due in June 2023 as output of “Task 3.4 Collaboration tools and services integration”.

As documented in the COESO project description of action, this task is mainly aimed at developing connectors to applications. The VERA system has been designed to be technology agnostic allowing the use of both open and proprietary services (when used).

VERA is a web platform that facilitates collaboration and it is centered around participatory research projects. Since collaboration nowadays already happens on a multitude of digital services and tools, therefore the approach was not to invent new tools for the community, but rather integrate into VERA those that users already use in their daily routine, to have a single access hub to all of them from the project dashboard.

The selected Collaborative Tools are third-party web applications that have not been developed in the context of the COESO project and that were integrated into VERA to facilitate project collaboration.

The integration of Collaborative Tools has been directly implemented into VERA as one of the project setup sections, where users can select the tools used by the project and add the direct link to them.

I. Structure of the document

This document is structured in III sections:

- Section I: Executive summary
- Section II: Description of the collaboration tools
- Section III: Conclusions

II. VERA Collaboration tools

In this section we detail how the integration of collaboration tools was implemented.

During the co-design workshops organised within the user research task (Task 3.1 User research and user experience design), the aim of the first workshops was to investigate which external tools the users of VERA would have liked to have at their disposal on the platform.

As documented in D3.1 User experience and user interface design¹ participants in the workshop were asked to list the tools and services they have used in their previous and current collaboration projects and those they would like to find available in the VERA platform.

This initial base of tools was implemented as integration into VERA already in its first beta release in December 2022.

This integration with tools is being fine tuned in the project lifespan through the addition of new tools suggested by the community.

When creating a project, one of the tabs is dedicated to the selection of the tools that will be used by the team as shown in the picture below:

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/6523503>

Figure 1 - Tools selection tab

These tools have been grouped according to 11 specific categories that have been identified in the analysis of collaboration within participatory research projects as discussed in the co-design workshops:

- Video conference
- File storage and sharing
- Word processor
- Web communication platform
- Calendar
- Blog
- Email
- Social networks
- Meeting scheduling
- Personal notes
- Mobile instant messaging

Under each category, there is a list of the most used tools as shown in the picture below. These tools are a mix of commercial and open source tools.

Figure 2 - Detail of video conferencing tools list

By clicking on “add to project” button, these tools are added to the project dashboard. The selected tools can always be updated from the project admin panel.

Once the list of tools is set up, it is then possible to customize each selected tool, by adding a direct link to it from the project homepage. The following pictures shows the view of the selected tools and the admin panel to add the customized links:

Figure 3 - Project homepage with tools shortcuts

Figure 4 - Selection of "Add link" button

Figure 5 - Insertion of customized link

Figure 6 - Editing of deletion of tool link

III. Conclusions

This deliverable provides a description of the integration of tools into the VERA platform. The successful integration of existing tools is crucial for supporting the diverse range of practices found in citizen science projects in the social sciences and humanities (SSH).

In order to ensure that the tools section meets the needs of users, it has been enriched with valuable suggestions from the platform's users and through rigorous user testing. This iterative process has helped refine the selection of tools and improve their overall usability within VERA.

While the current list of tools is already quite comprehensive, the future development of the tools section will include enhancements to further expand its capabilities. One possible evolution is to enable users to add their own tools to the project dashboard, providing them with the flexibility to incorporate tools that are specific to their project requirements. This feature would allow users to tailor the platform to their unique needs, without being limited to a predefined list of tools.

In addition to user customization, the tools section also has the potential to promote the use of open-source software. Open-source software has numerous advantages, including transparency, community-driven development, and accessibility. To encourage its adoption, the VERA platform could consider highlighting open-source tools with a green flag or by providing recommendations for open-source alternatives alongside commercial tools. This would not only support the open-source community but also empower users to make informed choices when selecting tools for their projects.

By continuously improving and expanding the tools section, VERA aims to create a dynamic and inclusive environment for citizen science SSH projects. The integration of existing tools, incorporation of user feedback, and potential for user customization and open-source promotion all contribute to the platform's goal of accommodating a wide range of project practices and fostering collaboration in the field of citizen science in the SSH domain.